

ORION | Trapezium

A Monthly Publication of the ORION Astronomical Society

This is an image of the planet Saturn, showing its moon Titan and Titan's shadow as they transit across the planet. This image was captured by John Cliff at his home observatory 5.8 km ESE of TAO, early on the morning of 20 Sep 2025. For more details, see the Astrophotography section inside.

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Page Three Astronomy

***The Search for Alien Life:
The Truth is Out There***

The **ORION Astronomical Society** is a science and astronomy group founded in April 1974 by scientists from the United States Department of Energy facilities at Oak Ridge, Tennessee. We primarily serve the communities of Oak Ridge and Knoxville and the counties of Anderson, Knox, and Roane.

ORION's mission is to support scientific research, teaching, and astronomical activities in East Tennessee. We hold monthly public meetings at the Oak Ridge RSCC Campus, and are active at Tamke-Allan Observatory (TAO), hosting public events, sharing knowledge of the skies, and helping to provide intellectually stimulating programs. ORION works to share the wonders of the cosmos and the culture of science.

ORION members include scientists, engineers, technicians, IT experts, artists, students, and others with varied talents and expertise. Over half of ORION members own telescopes, many are amateur radio operators, and some have expertise in astrophotography.

ORION has working relationships with several organizations, including museums and other amateur astronomy groups. Membership is open to individuals who will actively contribute their time and ideas. The annual membership fee is \$20, and student discounts are available. There is no charge for our newsletters and publications, or for participation in most ORION activities.

ORION Board and Officers:

President: Don Spong

VP and Program Chair: David Fields

Social Chair: Noah Frere

Secretary: Rob Fowler

Treasurer: Bob Edwards

Editor: Ted Barnes

Astrotechnologist: Rob Scott

Videographer: Rob Fowler

Obed Site Outreach: Joshua Gray.

TRAPEZIUM is a monthly publication of the ORION Astronomical Society. The issue date is the Friday preceding the monthly ORION meeting, chosen to provide timely information regarding the planned Program.

From March 2025 we will be working towards issuing a somewhat shorter version of the Trapezium, which will still include important information regarding the monthly ORION presentation, as well as dates and other information regarding Public Stargazes and other notable events relating to ORION and TAO.

Regarding the contents of this revised Trapezium, we have already concluded that some components, such as a separate Astrophotography section, are so important for a publication on amateur astronomy that one really cannot justify excluding them.

Messages from ORION

We've recently had some successful stargazing nights with favorable weather at Tamke-Allan (September 20, October 2 and 4). Thanks to the weather gods and all those who participated. There's been a lot of astronomy in the news recently related to three comets: 3I/Atlas, C/2025 R2 (SWAN), and Lemmon (C/2025 A6). 3I/Atlas, the interstellar visitor, continues to attract attention due to speculation that it might be an alien probe. This has been fueled by Abraham Loeb of Harvard University and collaborators at the Initiative for Interstellar Studies in the UK. They've written a paper on arXiv: 2507.12213 exploring the anomalous photometric and astrometric characteristics of 3I/Atlas and then going on to describe the orbital changes it could make while passing behind the sun if its intention were to intercept the Earth (which could come in late November/early December); so hold on to your hats! However, in the conclusion they write: "By far the most likely outcome will be that 3I/ATLAS is a completely natural interstellar object, probably a comet." In any event there will potentially be some viewing opportunities for 3I/ATLAS in the early morning hours of early November, but it will be significantly fainter than C/2025 R2 (SWAN) (by 190 times) or Lemmon (C/2025 A6) (by 120 times).

In October the full moon (known as the Harvest Moon) is October 6 and the new moon is October 21. As mentioned above there are several comets around. Lemmon (C/2025 A6) is visible currently in the early morning hours, and is well positioned high in the sky. It is approaching a brightness level soon where it will be naked eye visible. C/2025 R2 (SWAN) is an evening comet, but is low in the sky (about 17 degrees above the horizon). 3I/Atlas is dim and about to go behind the sun, but there may be better opportunities to image it in November. Planets that are currently in good position are Saturn, Neptune, and Uranus. Jupiter doesn't show up until around 1am. There is a meteor shower, the Orionids, coming up October 20, 21. Fortunately, this is the same time as the new moon, so viewing conditions should be ideal, weather permitting. Some of the deep-sky objects of interest this month are:

President's Message (cont.)

M57, the Ring Nebula in the constellation Lyra, about 2500 ly away; NGC 7000, the North American Nebula in Cygnus, also about 2500 ly away; NGC 2826, the Blinking Planetary Nebula, also in Cygnus, about 2000 ly away; NGC 7293, the Helix Nebula in Aquarius, about 650 ly away; the star cluster M15 in Pegasus, about 35,700 ly away, M31, the Andromeda galaxy, in Andromeda, and about 2.2 Mly away; and NGC 7331, Stephan's quintet, also in Andromeda, about 50 Mly away.

TAO Director's Message / Observatory Way :

The ORION Sky Ruler

David Fields

October 2025

The photo on the left shows our new road sign for Roane State's Tamke-Allan Observatory (TAO). Traveling West on Caney Creek Road from Roane County Park, the sign appears on the left just after crossing Joiner Hollow Road.

TAO Public Stargazes and Special Events

TAO offers Public Stargazes to the community on the 1st and 3rd Saturday of each month, weather permitting. Our usual schedule for the summer is to open at 8:30 pm and continue to nominally 10:30 pm -- later when the sky and attendance encourage this. Opening time changes according to the season, and a good guide is to arrive at the observatory about sunset, when weather is encouraging. These Stargazes are supported by local astronomy clubs, especially ORION members and friends, and benefit our students and community. Our TAO Stargazes are usually well attended, with a full classroom of visitors for evening astronomy lectures.

What are rulers and Sky Rulers? Where do we carry them?

A ruler is a tool for measurement of linear distance. Measurement can be a tool for understanding. **We can define a Sky Ruler as a tool for measuring angular separation of objects in the sky.** Let's explore the need, the history of celestial angular measurement, and possible design for a modern Sky Ruler.

In general, a ruler is useful only when it is in the hands of the user. For a hiker with a map, the ruler is in his hand with his map and compass. For a designer or engineer, the ruler is on his desk. For a medical technician, the same.

Observatory Way (cont.)

For an astronomer, the sky ruler must be close at hand – in his/her pocket, or hidden on a reticle in his telescope eyepiece, or be part of a computer program. Once a telescope is aligned with the sky the astronomer may rely on the computer for many things, but if there is no computer, the astronomer needs the Sky Ruler in his pocket. So, how may we obtain or design such a ruler? And how do we get it into the hands of ORION members and TAO students?

The Sky Ruler should also present physical constants, show linear measurements (inches and cm), be inexpensive so we can give away as many as we like, identify ORION as a research-oriented group of enthusiastic, fact-oriented astronomers, and delight ORION members and students.

This was the challenge I posed to our ORION board last Monday. We're still thinking about this, so let us know your suggestions. Meanwhile, here are some background thoughts.

Astronomy Rulers

This photo shows a plastic ruler that ORION gave to RSCC students and ORION members a few years ago, together with another of my favorite astronomy rulers:

The ORION ruler (above) fulfilled several purposes. It was a nice Christmas gift to ORION members and students, plus it introduced students in my Astronomy classes to the idea that ‘measurements’ are important. It also introduced the metric system. It was an example of how ORION helps the college, in addition to helping the students with astronomy, and introducing astronomy and the night sky at our TAO stargazes. I wished

Observatory Way (cont.)

many times that it included much more information, but we found a nice price, provided that we kept the information short and simple.

The TVIW ruler (in the image below) provided a perspective on the distance to the closest star systems, and presented some of the physical constants that define our system of units.

These were both useful rulers, but they had disadvantages. The ORION ruler was durable, but too costly to give away in large numbers. TVIW ruler was made of cheap cardboard, but the TVIW ruler was inexpensive, so many were distributed. Both were good rulers, but they did not give a sense of measuring the sky – they were not actual “Sky Rulers.”

A disadvantage of both rulers was that at a length of 6.5,” they didn’t easily fit into a shirt pocket or a wallet. What rulers might avoid these issues? Here are two examples, and I usually carry both:

Special-purpose rulers often have special functions that convert linear measures to other values, such as those for engineers (left, for a folded triangular ruler for dimensional scaling) and for medical technicians (right).

Observatory Way (cont.)

Designing a Sky Ruler for Astronomers

A Sky Ruler should permit measurements of angular distances in the sky. This would be useful to star-hop from known bright stars or Constellations. It should also present physical constants, show linear measurements (inches and cm), be inexpensive so we can give away as many as we like, identify ORION as a research-oriented group of enthusiastic, fact-oriented astronomers, and delight ORION members and students. It should stay close at hand, fitting the wallet and/or shirt pocket. Thus it might be business-card size, or it might be a 5" or 6" ruler that could be folded.

Does a "modern" astronomer need a Sky Ruler? Certainly a modern astronomer needs a 'normal' ruler for linear measurements on a star chart or across a computer screen. Then one might convert mathematically to actual distances, or to angular degrees for telescope positioning. Yes, for measurements of eyepiece holder diameter (maybe 0.96" for a valuable antique telescope), or eyepiece optical aperture, or the required length of a USB cable, or defining one of the similar computer connectors -- a ruler is a necessary tool for an astronomer.

It's not difficult to estimate angles in the sky if one knows a little trigonometry, and can do arithmetic mentally. But most beginners and students do not fit this pattern. Many amateur astronomers struggle to find objects in the sky unless they have an aligned telescope close at hand. Introducing students to the sky can be difficult without reference points and a way to scale distances. In my classes, they first learn some Constellations and bright stars. They must also learn to estimate angles, but for some this is difficult.

So yes, there is a need for a Sky Ruler. Let's discover how to include a Sky Ruler on our astronomer's kit. A most useful ruler for an astronomer would be one that measures not only linear distances, but also angular distances in the sky. The earliest such rules of thumb for sky angles were probably based on finger widths and hand spans; the angle was based on the width of the chosen finger or a span at arm's length.

Observatory Way (cont.)

The hand Sky Ruler was approximate and not useful unless one had an excellent memory or some tattoos.

Instruments were invented to measure celestial angles and to provide better reliability and accuracy than afforded by hands. These rulers had names such as cross-staff (or Jacob's staff, left illustration) and sextant (right illustration). Although useful, they do not meet our goals of low cost, reproducibility, and reasonable size.

Construction and use of a cross-staff can be both fun and instructive. (See <https://www.skyatnightmagazine.com/advice/make-a-sky-ruler>.)

Modern Celestial Angle Rulers for Astronomers

Are there any modern sky rulers in common use? My favorite, after sometimes using the apps on my iPhone (most apps are not very good for measuring angles), is the Telrad finder – a reticle-equipped star finder that shows angular size of celestial objects. The target shows circles of 3 diameters: 0.5, 2, and 4 degrees. The Telrad finder is large, and mounts on a telescope. It is an excellent tool for orienting a telescope, and is useful for angle measurements below 4 degrees.

At a cost of about \$50, and fragile, it doesn't meet our goals, but it can be a useful instrument.

Observatory Way (cont.)

A Sky Ruler for ORION

We have reached a design point for our Sky Ruler:

- Construction: Light-weight, plastic or paper, perhaps transparent
- Cost: Low
- Size: Standard business card size (to fit shirt pocket or wallet), or 5" ruler, to be folded
- Linear Distance scale: cm and probably inches
- Angular Distance scale: arc-degrees on two edges
Long edge: about 10 arc deg for standard business card held at arm's length
Short edge: about 6 arc deg for standard business card held at arm's length
- Information Included:
Physical constants from TVIW ruler
QR code for ORION and TAO
www.orioninc.org
www.roanestate.edu/obs
www.ORIONastronomy+subscribe@groups.io
Map
Oak Ridge Isochronous Observation Network on
www.astrospheric.com

Calculating angular distances between stars

This discussion has been about measurement, but if one wishes to calculate the angle between two stars from their celestial coordinates, there is a simple formula for that angle in terms of their right ascensions (RAs) and declinations (Decs). If α_1 and α_2 are the RAs and δ_1 and δ_2 the Decs of the two stars, the cosine of the angle θ between them is given by $\cos \theta = \cos \delta_1 \cos \delta_2 \cos (\alpha_2 - \alpha_1) + \sin \delta_1 \sin \delta_2$. One may evaluate θ using a table or a calculator, or by writing a simple line of code. Of course a few of the more dramatic cases could be included in an astronomy data card.

ORION Board Meetings ElCantarito

- Rob Fowler

This is a summary of topics discussed recently at the weekly (Monday 1 pm) ORION Board Meeting held as a regular working lunch at ElCantarito restaurant in Oak Ridge. Notes as contributed in Stardate format by Sec. Rob Fowler.

Stardate: 2025.03.31

In attendance were Robert Fowler, Ted Barnes, David Fields, Art Alison and Don Spong. Discussed delays on new dome report due to committee participant availability. Discussed possible going to TAO Tuesday night. Discussed next speaker is not firm for April's meeting. Discussed voting for officers at the next ORION Meeting. Discussed the next Friendship Stargaze and date for same, 8th possibly. Discussed possibly coming up with cloudy night entertainment for Friendship stargaze. Discussed Wordsworth poem about telescopes. Discussed potential security cams for TAO.

Stardate: 2025.04.07

In attendance were David Fields, Art Alison, Ted Barnes and Rob Fowler. Ted discussed the data acquired from his Arduino/LED test. David discussed a mount having the ability to track asteroids via PHD2. David discussed the Friendship Stargaze is 7:30pm Tuesday. Discussed needing pics of new concrete pads at TAO.

Stardate: 2025.04.14

In attendance were David, Ted, Art and Rob. Ted discussed results of the 785 Zwetana occultation. After a long and dramatic story, Ted revealed a successful capture. Noah is reaching out to Joe Baldwin about next month's presentation. Ted discussed quantum field theory using functional methods.

Stardate: 2025.04.21

In attendance were David Fields, Ted Barnes, Art Alison, Noah Frere and Rob Fowler. Ted discussed how to use AnyDesk and log in unattended. Ted discussed a planetary occultation, Mars vs a 9th magnitude star on May 6th at 1 am. David discussed progress he is making with a Meshtastic receiver. Mention of 4 visitors who showed up at TAO and new member Kevin Wilson. David brought up calendar access .Discussed problem with rotation of glow dome lid. Watch for migration of wheel axles. One axle migrated in and caused the lid to bind.

ORION Board Meetings (cont.)

Stardate: 2025.04.28

In attendance were David Fields, Ted Barnes, Art Alison, Kevin Wilson, John Cliff and Rob Fowler. Briefly mentioned domes on CloudyNights.com. Ted discussed upcoming Mars/Star occultation and relevant challenges. HD 74058 vs Mars just after midnight 00:44 night 5th/6th morn. TAO Stargaze beginning at May 3rd 8pm. Friendship Stargaze possibly May 6th. Briefly discussed avoiding Feynman's van. Shared astrophotos. Discussed potentially going to TAO tonight & Noah's class.

Stardate: 2025.05.05

In attendance were David Fields, Art Alison, Ted Barnes, Kevin Wilson, and Rob Fowler. David asked if we have a set program for May. That remains unclear. Ted contacted Noah to confirm. We await a reply. Ted mentioned the next annual IOTA meeting is possibly going to be in New Mexico in Oct.

Stardate: 2025.05.12

At 11am David, Ted & Art met at the Library and made a first pass as setting up a display case for the club. Rob joined later. It was artistically done, decorated with a small telescope, some antique books, and astrophotos. Discussed whether Kevin might give the May lecture and what topics he has ready. He agreed to speak on the topic of stellar spectroscopy. Ted mentioned the next possible occultation on the early morning on 5/21/2025.

Stardate: 2025.05.19

In attendance were Don, David, Ted, Art, Kevin, and Rob. Kevin brought up Benjamin Baniker as a potential lecturer. Rob announced that the most recent lecture is on YouTube.

Star Date: 2025.05.26

In attendance were Don, Dave, Art & Rob. David suggested improvements to the Meade's power supply in hopes of reducing noise, higher amperage power supply, adding ferrite cores. Dave discussed getting a construction party to begin construction on the Dob shelter. Discussed parking issues at TAO.

ORION Board Meetings (cont.)

Stardate: 2025.06.02

In attendance were Don, David, Bob, Art, Juan, Kevin and Noah (and Sunny). We met early at the library to discuss the current and new display box. Discussed meeting again, tomorrow (Tuesday). David suggested Wednesday night 8:30pm as the next Friendship Stargaze. Kevin suggested meeting at TAO to look at the Meade's encoder. Noah suggested reaching out to Gareth Davis to see if he has any potential acquaintances for another lecture. Don asked about the new dome project. David responded with a tale of woe regarding the Roane purchasing project.

Stardate: 2025.06.09

In attendance were Don, David, Art and Rob (joined by John Rather). David purchased 2 coin cells for the Celestron CGM mount. He also purchased a few ferrite cores to suppress noise from the power supply. Ted expressed an interest in having help with this months Trapezium. Discussed the new optical telescope coming online in the Atacama Desert. Briefly mentioned the library displays and Oak Ridge street lighting. Noah mentioned that Gareth Davis can give the next lecture.

Stardate: 2025.06.16

In attendance were Don, Kevin, Art and Rob. Rob showed his submission for the AMSE poster. Kevin & Don discussed PixInsight. We confirmed Kevin is speaking this month. Kevin discussed the Astronomical League and it's various programs, and contests for various achievements.

Stardate: 2025.06.23

Due to crowding at the table, no notes were taken. In attendance were Don, David, Ted, Art, Kevin and Robert.

Stardate: 2025.06.30

In attendance were David, Ted, Art, Kevin, and Rob. Don sat in for a short while. Ted & Rob discussed results of the occultation via a new process. Kevin presented a new ORION Logo. Kevin announced he will be moving out of the immediate area.

ORION Board Meetings (cont.)

Stardate: 2025.06.30

David presented Kevin with a gift ORION T-Shirt. David brought up shop type measurements he intends to do on the Meade. The group went on discuss various theoretical topics. Mention of 4 visitors who showed up at TAO and new member Kevin Wilson David brought up calendar access. Discussed problem with rotation of glow dome lid. Watch for migration of wheel axels. One axel migrated in and caused the lid to bind.

Stardate: 2025.07.07

In attendance were Don, Ted, David, Art, Rob and visitor John Rather. Conversations opened with Ted discussing digitizing the occultation substacking project. David discussed a lightstrip project and possible application in the dome. Ted collected info for this month's Trapezium. David discussed attendance at the Sat July 5 Public Star Gaze, was 12, give or take. David discussed the testing we did on the Meade and saw no alignment errors.

Stardate: 2025.07.14

In attendance were David, Ted, Art and Rob. Ted shared some mathematical analysis of the recent occultation data. David brought up potential dates for the next Friendship Star Gaze. We discussed the next ORION lecture and whether to zoom it or not. We discussed possibly having a news feature at ORION lectures.

Stardate: 2025.07.21

In attendance were David, Don, Ted, Art, Rob... and guest John. Dave led the discussion with Rob's absence. Dave mentioned that Saturday night's public star gaze was successful, with around 8 visitors. We discussed the recent lecture and the unplanned move to the computer classroom. The general consensus is that it went well. Dave will be away on August 2nd, the next star gaze. Ted brought up details of participation in the Tuesday night / Wednesday morning occultation.

Stardate: 2025.07.28

In attendance were David Fields, Ted Barnes, Art Alison and Rob Fowler We will probably have a public star gaze at TAO on 8/2/2025, public or private depending on weather and Noah's decision. 8/12/2025 Perseid meteor shower a probable star gaze.

ORION Board Meetings (cont.)

Stardate: 2025.07.28

Our Library display will expire soon. David will inquire if we can keep it another month or if we need to clean it out this month. If it has to come down, Ted & Rob have agreed to remove the contents.

Stardate: 2025.08.04

Present were Don, Ted, Rob, Art and guest John Rather. Ted shared his most recent results and submission to IOTA that we have been re-evaluating. Don won't be present for the August ORION meeting. We believe John Cliff is August's speaker. We discussed various lightning phenomenon We also discussed the Big Bang theory and John Rather's book.

Stardate: 2025.08.11

Present were Don, Ted, David, Art, Rob and guests Richard Piety and John Rather. Ted reported on some of his recent results with IOTA's python scripts and graphing. Rob reported on visiting Lily Bluff's Star Party at Wartburg, where he met Joshua, Gareth and Owen. Don told us of a new 16 bit color astro camera he just bought, a ZWO ASI2600MCP. John told us of an experience with a pro telescope. Richard just bought a QHY174M-GPS camera for recording timed asteroid occultations. We discussed weather regarding the Perseid meteor / stargaze, 8:30pm Tuesday, but the weather is deteriorating. There is a possible occultation on 8/23/25.

Star date: 2025.08.18

In attendance were Ted, David, Art, Rob and guests John Rather and Richard Piety. David spoke to Courtney at AMSE about our ORION display. We have been invited to keep it set up for a while longer. We discussed possibly tracking 3I/ATLAS to get a pic, having an unscheduled observation evening.

Star Date: 2025.08.25

In attendance were Dave, Ted, Richard and Rob. Ted shared the results of the recent asteroid occultation. David visited the K-25 interpretive center and described the layout. He said they are interested in us bringing a star party to that location. David noticed that one of the new pads in collecting water. Rob suggested a modified a port-a-potty as a camouflage telescope cover. Calling it "Astro-Johnny: Smelling like Roses!"

ORION Board Meetings (cont.)

Star Date: 2025.09.01

In attendance were David Fields, Ted Barnes, Art Alison and Rob Fowler. And visitor David Allred. David Fields fixed the internet with at TAO and treated several ant colonies. The skies were good from 9pm to Midnight. Discussed an upcoming eclipse in Sydney Australia in 2 years. Ted spoke to the programmer of Occult Watcher [Hristo Pavlov] who helped him troubleshoot a bug. IOTA Annual meeting is next week on zoom.

Star Date: 2025.09.08

In attendance were David Fields, Ted Barnes, Rob Fowler, Don Spong, Art Alison and Richard Piety. We has a successful Moon-gaze at TAO last night. Ted discussed his occultation studies. He was successful with one last night Sunday 2025.09.07. Richard attempted it too but has not analyzed his results yet. We had a new guest last night, Art's friend Deirdre Akin. She joined the astro-luncheon as well.

Star Date: 2025.09.15

In attendance were David Fields, Ted Barnes, Don Spong, Rob Fowler and Richard Piety.

- We discussed concerns over who is coordinating speakers going forward.
- Tentatively, we believe Gareth Davies is our September speaker.
- We discussed news about the cosmic interloper 3I/Atlas and new spectral data.

ORION Board Meeting at the ElCantarito Mexican Restaurant, Oak Ridge, Mon 22 Sep 2025. L to R: Ted Barnes, David Allred, David Fields, Richard Piety, Rob Fowler, and Gareth Davies.

ORION Board Meetings (cont.)

Star Date: 2025.09.22

In attendance were David Fields, Ted Barnes, Robert Fowler, Richard Piety and guest, David Alred.

Gareth Davis, Art Allison, and Don Spong arrive later.

- Ted and Richard discussed results of a recent occultation.
- Richard caught 2 new occultations recently.
- David expressed concerns over the success of last Saturday's Stargaze. He felt distracted and so thought it did not go well. But several of us thought it went very well.
- Gareth Discussed cosmic interloper 3I/Atlas, and its tail having recently turned green.
- Richard Piety confirmed that the ORION website is badly out of date.
- To support Public Star gazes, David discussed having teams of 2 to operate the Meade.
- Gareth talked about an astrophysicist, David Butler, who has a Youtube channel.

Star Date: 2025.09.29

In attendance were Don, Ted, David, Richard, Art and Robert.

- Ted told us about his visit to New Mexico and the skies at Cloudcroft.
- David asked about an abstract for October's guest speaker, Joshua from OBED.
- We discussed possibly meeting at TAO on Wednesday or Thursday.

Star Date: 2025.10.06

In attendance were David Fields, Don Spong, Ted Barnes, Rob Fowler & Art Allison.

- David suggested we create something as a giveaway to members and students. He suggested a plastic ruler to help people understand angles. He also discussed making a custom planisphere.
- We discussed using Night Sky Network to coerce dues compliance. Art took up the challenge of creating a new giveaway / print project.
- Although this month's speaker is confirmed, no details have been communicated.
- Etymology needed for the expressions "cattiewumpus" and "whackadoodle."

ORION Monthly Meetings

ORION Monthly Meeting Format

Meeting Venue: City Room (A-111), just inside the main entrance, Coffey/McNalley Bldg., Oak Ridge Campus, Roane State Community College.

7:00 pm Eastern, 3rd Wednesday of each month.

Our monthly meetings (except for December, a dinner) generally proceed as follows:

- Welcome
- Announcements
- Invited Presentation and Discussion
- Awarding of the Mug
- Astrophotography / Special Presentations

The nominal start time is 7:00 pm Eastern, on the 3rd Wednesday of the month. The beginning of the meeting will usually include announcements of general interest.

Meetings typically continue until around 9:00 pm. Please plan to stay until the end. Hopefully we will all enjoy the astrophotography and other special topics discussed in the latter part of the meeting.

Remote Viewing: A live Zoom session will usually be open during the ORION Monthly Meeting, at the link:

<https://us02web.zoom.us/j/88528735960?pwd=KzY4bnBHcjlhTzg3L3pOcjY0TFovUT09> or
<https://bit.ly/42apGxX>

Meeting ID: 885 2873 5960 Passcode: 716689

Title: Astronomy at the Obed WSR**Speaker: Joshua Gray****Park Ranger & Night Sky Coordinator
Obed Wild & Scenic River****Abstract:**

As a full-time ranger with the National Park Service, Josh wears many hats to serve the public. Examples of the duties he is in charge of include:

- Operates the visitor center in downtown Wartburg, TN, providing information to park visitors 7 days a week.
- Providing night sky programs and conducting meetings/research with Dark Sky International.
- Collaborates with Big South Fork, Manhattan Project, and Frozen Head State Park rangers for festivals, programs, and other events.
- Speaks to students at Morgan County Schools for career days, STEM nights, and other educational events.

When he's not at work, he likes to spend nights at home with his wife Bergen, and their rambunctious 10 month old dog, Jett. He loves to spend time on Watts Bar Lake with his in-laws, and loves watching hockey.

His talk will focus on the educational opportunities that Obed is providing to the public each and every month, especially highlighting the attendance of night sky programs. He will also give an update on the status of getting Big South Fork certified as a international night sky park, and the continued cooperation with Frozen Head State Park and Pickett C.C.C. Memorial State Park.

ORION Last Month – 17 Sep 2025

ORION President Don Spong opens the 17 Sep 2025 ORION Monthly Meeting.

ORION Last Month (cont.)

The Lightest and Heaviest Elements and their Isotopes as Powerful Groundwater Tracers - Gareth Davies

Our featured speaker for the ORION Presentation on 17 Sep 2025 was Gareth Davies, who earlier this year (16 Apr) had given an ORION presentation on “The Younger Dryas Cold Event” of 12.9 kyrs BP, which has a possible attribution to a cosmic impact. In his Sep 2025 presentation Gareth discussed the history of and recent results in using tracers to determine subsurface water flow. The audience was clearly enthused by this presentation, which had considerable ORNL relevance, and was entertained by the many surprising results reviewed in this talk.

The audience for Gareth's 17 Sep ORION Presentation.

ORION Last Month (cont.)

Groundwater Models + Tracing = Surprise?

- Groundwater flow models using a homogeneous setting are always wrong in karst/fractured rocks
- Injected tracing in karst, shows rapid velocities, km/day
- Even in the clastic (shaley) rocks, velocities of 10 - 100 m/day
- At scale of 100's of m to <10 km

Gareth's deep dive into an amazing series of unexpected tracer results.

ORION Last Month (cont.)

Don offers the thirsty audience a tasty ZWO-flavored beverage.

Events and Calendars, Sky Maps and Occultations

Star, Moon, Comet and Meteorgazing at TAO in 2025

We enthusiastically invite visitors to attend our Public Stargaze events, held at our dark-sky site, the Tamke-Allan Observatory (TAO) near Kingston, Tennessee. These events are intended especially for visitors, so our buildings and facilities will be open, and there will be astronomy talks as well as public skywatching.

In Jan-Jun 2025 we plan to hold fixed-calendar public Stargaze events on the 1st and 3rd Saturday of each month. These weekend events are especially appropriate for families. We also hold public special events, such as a “Full Moonrise,” with associated Moon Music, and the occasional comet watch. The annual Perseid Meteor watch in mid-August is especially popular.

The precise dates of many of these events depend on the local weather conditions, and cannot be specified *definitively* long in advance. As an approximate guide, see the TAOCalendar pages following. Once a date is finalized we usually confirm it through the ORION online message site ORION astronomy@groups.io. Likely and unlikely dates for TAO events may be inferred from the weather predictions at TAO by Clear Sky Charts (cleardarksky dot com) and Astrospheric (astrospheric dot com).

Please confirm event dates before proceeding to TAO.

In view of the rather challenging approach road to TAO, “Observatory Way,” first-time visitors should plan to arrive before dark. Driving instructions are given at: <https://www.roanestate.edu/pages/obs/visit.htm>

Some instructions follow, since people may be unfamiliar with procedures for stargazing at a dark-sky site.

ORION members are invited to arrive early with their telescopes and mounts, to prepare for evening observing and to share refreshments. Please bring a red flashlight, or a headband with a red-light option.

Visitors who wish to acquire red lights or red-light headbands for observing may find them at many commercial amateur astronomy sites, such as [https:// www dot high pointscientific dot com](https://www.highpointscientific.com). The “Lepro LE” LED Headlamp, model 3200008, available from Amazon for about \$10 (Aug. 2024) is a personal favorite. This is rechargeable and has separate red and white led buttons, with several brightness settings. A caution: For amateur astronomy, brighter lights are NOT preferred, and WHITE lights are highly discouraged. Please use only red lights while the Stargaze is in progress.

Parking is available on site; on entering TAO **stay to the right**, and *please use the parking area below and right (Southwest) of the TAO buildings and observing area, near the treeline*. And **PLEASE NO HEADLIGHTS ON SITE.**

Visitors are encouraged to interact with ORION astronomers who have set up and may be operating telescopes and other astronomical equipment. We enjoy public discussions, and regard this sharing of information as a primary goal of our organization. Visitors are welcome to coffee and other refreshments.

TAO Public Stargazing: A Note Regarding Scheduling and Access in 2025

In 2025 we are reverting to an earlier schedule of having our Public Stargaze nights on every first and third Saturday. Of course this assumes good weather; if the weather is not suitable, a changed schedule will be announced on the group site [ORIONastronomy @ groups.io](mailto:ORIONastronomy@groups.io).

We decided that the previous (2024) schedule of a once-monthly Public Stargaze was insufficient, and having a Moon visible in some phase other than close to New gives our visitors an obvious and interesting object for viewing.

During Daylight Savings Time (mid-March through early November) we plan to hold our Public Stargaze events over the hours of approximately 8:00 pm - 11:00 pm, with some nominal variation.

If it is already dark when you arrive, please dim your headlights on the TAO grounds, follow the right branch of the access road, and park to the right of the TAO building, near the treeline.

Note: Parking in or near the elevated flat observing area at the front (East) of the TAO building is reserved for astronomers who are bringing their equipment.

Additional information for visitors may be found on the previous page and following two pages of this issue.

TAO Public Stargazes in October: Sats 04 & 18 Oct 2025

Sat 04 Oct 2025

Sunset	7:18 pm
Civ dusk	7:44 pm
Ast dusk	8:43 pm
Moonrise	5:58 pm
Moonset*	5:46 am
	*05 Oct

Moon illum. 91%

Waxing Gibbous Moon.
Nearly Full Moon during this event.

Sat 18 Oct 2025

Sunset	6:59 pm
Civ dusk	7:25 pm
Ast dusk	8:25 pm
Moonrise	5:03 am
Moonset	5:37 pm

Moon illum. 8%

Waning Crescent Moon.
No Moon visible during this event.

TAO Public Stargazes in November: Sats 01 & 15 Nov 2025

Sat 01 Nov 2025

Sunset	6:43 pm
Civ dusk	7:10 pm
Ast dusk	8:10 pm
Moonrise	4:23 pm
Moonset*	3:31 am
	*02 Nov

Moon illum. 79%

Waxing Gibbous Moon.
Bright Moon during this event.

Sat 15 Nov 2025

Sunset	6:32 pm
Civ dusk	6:59 pm
Ast dusk	8:01 pm
Moonrise	3:56 am
Moonset	4:04 pm

Moon illum. 19%

Waning Crescent Moon.
No Moon visible during this event.

TAO Calendars

Jan-Jun 2025; Aug & Sep 2025

The principle public events for visitors at TAO are the **Public Stargazes**, held at TAO during 2025 on the 1st and 3rd Saturday of each month. These are listed in the “**Public Fixed Events**” **TAO Calendar** for six month periods, currently Jul-Dec 2025. These appear on the page following.

Additional notable events will be included in monthly “**Special Events**” **TAO Calendars**. These include public events that do not have a fixed date long in advance, such as the **International Friendship Stargaze** in Oak Ridge, and special TAO events such as **Asteroid Occultations**, **Meteor Showers**, **Full Moonrises**, **Lunar (and other) Eclipses**, **Comet Watches**, and perhaps the occasional musical event.

These “Special Events” calendars for the current and subsequent months appear after the six-month “Public Fixed Events” calendar.

The facilities in the TAO buildings onsite will be open to the public during the “Public Fixed Events,” and will also usually be available when TAO is open to the public for some of the “Special Events.” **Please inquire regarding whether TAO will be open to the public for any “Special Event” you may wish to attend, since some may be restricted.** We will of course always try to accommodate enthusiastic visitors.

We recommend checking a TAO website such as <http://www.roanestate.edu/obs> before visiting, to confirm that listed events will proceed as planned; weather conditions for example may require a cancellation or change of date.

TAO Calendar Public Stargaze

Jan-Jun 2025

date	event	details	start	end
Sat 04 Jan 2025	<small>cancelled</small> ★	1 st Sat Stargaze	7:00 pm	10:00 pm
Sat 18 Jan 2025	<small>cancelled</small> ★	3 rd Sat Stargaze	7:00 pm	10:00 pm
Sat 01 Feb 2025	★	1 st Sat Stargaze	7:00 pm	10:00 pm
Sat 15 Feb 2025	<small>canceled</small> ★	3 rd Sat Stargaze	7:00 pm	10:00 pm
Sat 01 Mar 2025	<small>canceled</small> ★	1 st Sat Stargaze	7:00 pm	10:00 pm
Sat 15 Mar 2025	<small>canceled</small> ★	3 rd Sat Stargaze	7:00 pm	10:00 pm
Sat 05 Apr 2025	<small>canceled</small> ★	1 st Sat Stargaze	8:00 pm	11:00 pm
Sat 19 Apr 2025	<small>canceled</small> ★	3 rd Sat Stargaze	8:00 pm	11:00 pm
Sat 03 May 2025	<small>canceled</small> ★	1 st Sat Stargaze	8:00 pm	11:00 pm
Sat 17 May 2025	★	3 rd Sat Stargaze	8:00 pm	11:00 pm
Sat 07 Jun 2025	<small>cancelled</small> ★	1 st Sat Stargaze	8:00 pm	11:00 pm
Sat 21 Jun 2025	★	3 rd Sat Stargaze	8:00 pm	11:00 pm

These 2025 TAO Public Stargaze events are scheduled for fixed calendar days during the weekend, which will hopefully prove convenient for many visitors with families, especially those bringing younger astronomers. Cancellations often take place in Winter and Spring, due to cold or icy conditions, or overcast and rainy skies.

TAO Calendar Public Stargaze

Jul-Dec 2025

date	event	details	start	end
Sat 05 Jul 2025	^{cancelled} ★	1 st Sat Stargaze	8:30 pm	11:30 pm
Sat 19 Jul 2025	★	3 rd Sat Stargaze	8:30 pm	11:30 pm
Sat 02 Aug 2025	^{cancelled} ★	1 st Sat Stargaze	8:30 pm	11:30 pm
Sat 16 Aug 2025	★	3 rd Sat Stargaze	8:30 pm	11:30 pm
Sun 07 Sep 2025	^{moved} ★	"1 st Sat" Stargaze	8:00 pm	11:00 pm
Sat 20 Sep 2025	★	3 rd Sat Stargaze	8:00 pm	11:00 pm
Sat 04 Oct 2025	★	1 st Sat Stargaze	7:30 pm	10:00 pm
Sat 18 Oct 2025	★	3 rd Sat Stargaze	7:30 pm	10:00 pm
Sat 01 Nov 2025	★	1 st Sat Stargaze	7:00 pm	10:00 pm
Sat 15 Nov 2025	★	3 rd Sat Stargaze	7:00 pm	10:00 pm
Sat 06 Dec 2025	★	1 st Sat Stargaze	6:30 pm	10:00 pm
Sat 20 Dec 2025	★	3 rd Sat Stargaze	6:30 pm	10:00 pm

These 2025 TAO Public Stargaze events are scheduled for fixed calendar days during the weekend, which will hopefully prove convenient for many visitors with families, especially those bringing younger astronomers. Cancellations often take place in Winter, due to cold or icy conditions, or overcast and rainy skies.

TAOCalendar Special Events

Oct 2025

date	event	details	start	end
Sat 04 Oct 2025		1 st Sat Public Stargaze	7:30 pm	10:00 pm
Mon 06 Oct 2025		Full Moon 11:47 pm Eastern		
Sat 18 Oct 2025		3 rd Sat Public Stargaze	7:30 pm	10:00 pm
Tue 21 Oct 2025		New Moon 08:25 am Eastern		

TAOCalendar Special Events

Nov 2025

date	event	details	start	end
Sat 01 Nov 2025		1 st Sat Public Stargaze	7:00 pm	10:00 pm
Wed 05 Nov 2025		Full Moon 08:19 am Eastern		
Sat 15 Nov 2025		3 rd Sat Public Stargaze	7:00 pm	10:00 pm
Thu 20 Nov 2025		New Moon 01:47 am Eastern		

Public Stargaze of Sat 20 Sep 2025

- Ted Barnes

After some online discussion of the best date for this event it was finally decided that the predicted weather for Sat 20 Sep had better prospects than Sun 21 Sep, so it was announced that this Public Stargaze would be on Sat 20 Sep, as planned. TAO was scheduled to open at 8 pm. Due to some inefficient planning I managed to arrive at the TAO Gate much earlier, around 7:35 pm, and settled in for a wait. Two cars soon joined me in the admissions queue, and I had a déjà vu of waiting to enter the Riverside Movie Theater in North Kansas City with my parents around 1960. It was already very dark as 8:00 pm approached, perhaps the opening time at this time of year should instead be 7:30 pm, so any first-time visitors would stand a chance in their first encounter with the TAO access road.

Sat 20 Sep 2025

Sunset	7:39 pm
Civ dusk	8:04 pm
Ast dusk	9:05 pm
Moonrise	6:10 am
Moonset	7:09 pm

Moon illum. 2%

Waning Crescent Moon.
No Moon visible during this event.

The surprisingly dark sky at TAO as of 8:19 pm Eastern, 20 Sep 2025.

Public Stargaze of Sat 20 Sep 2025 (cont.)

On arrival at TAO I learned that my other car-bound waitees had been Art Allison and Don Spong, who soon began setting up their observing equipment. Due to general personal exhaustion and the stress of planning a future vacation, I had decided not to bring my telescope to this event. Instead I thought I would just bring my camp chair, give a short astronomy talk to our visitors, and then settle in to the lawn chair with binoculars. Both of these activities proved difficult; I had upgraded my recent occultations talk, but left that version on a home computer, and failed to copy it onto the memory stick I brought. I had hoped as a backup to store it on a TAO computer, but AD failed to connect, so that didn't happen; no updated talk. No problem, David and Don gave talks. As for the binoculars, I had left them at home. So I admired the stars from a lawn chair without optical aid.

We had 8 visitors, these being our two SMAS colleagues, four of Noah's students and their friends, one with a charming little daughter, and Robert Corliss, who was very excited about a flyover by the Chinese Space Station. With myself, David Fields, Don Spong, Rob Fowler, Art Allison and Bob Edwards that makes 14. Or 15, once you include Sunny the Astrodog. A respectable group.

Don (foreground, with a surprisingly intense white light) and Art, setting up on the North and Northeast pads respectively.

Public Stargaze of Sat 20 Sep 2025 (cont.)

I had brought my “Meade kit” of useful items for the Meade LX-200, and after Rob started connecting things up I stopped by the glow dome to see if I could be of any assistance. Rob was just starting to align the system, so by pointing various lasers around and playing with the HC (antique hand controller) we managed to identify Nunki in the eyepiece. However all Rob really wanted was to show Saturn to our visitors, so we next simply pointed the OTA below the square of Pegasus and found it. Saturn presented a very pleasing image, the rings still being very narrow; one had the impression of a faint light cream colored disk with a spike through it. Our visitors all enjoyed it.

Above the glow dome one can easily distinguish Sagittarius (Sgr) and to the right, Scorpius, featuring Antares. And some whirls of cloud.

Public Stargaze of Sat 20 Sep 2025 (cont.)

For our next public image, since Hercules was well placed high in the West, we decided to show our visitors the famous Messier-listed globular cluster M13. After checking where it was in the “keystone,” aided by my Celestron SkyPortal app, Rob was able to find it relatively easily as a small grey smudge. Improved focus turned this into a patch with visible stars. Since the visitors were still in the TAO lecture room we decided to attach a camera, one of my ZWO ASI294MCPs, and Rob captured several stacks of this beautiful object. As the lectures were just finishing I encouraged our visitors to come out and see our new astrophotos of M13. They were quite interested to see the comparison between the faint naked-eye object in the eyepiece and the very bright image captured shortly earlier as a stack, using SharpCap. One of the Meade-LX200 stacked images of M13 is shown below, after post processing.

This image was taken using a ZWO ASI294MCP, and is a stack of 6 frames at a gain of 520, each frame just over 4 secs. The exposure midpoint time was 10:40:54 pm Eastern.

Public Stargaze of Sat 20 Sep 2025 (cont.)

Due to other commitments, Bob Edwards and Art Allison both departed early, at about 10 pm. After some time spent chatting, I departed about midnight, leaving Rob, David and Don still at TAO. It is easier to leave when you have brought little equipment, so this was a relatively simple departure. Don had been working on images of the Veil Nebula; we can see some of his work from this evening in the Astrophotography section of the current (Oct 2025) issue.

Occultation of star TYC 2436-00120-1 by asteroid 337 Devosa: Two Hours of Prep and 5 Minutes of Panic - Richard Piety

Early on Sunday morning Sep 21, 2025, I went out well before sunrise to get my equipment ready for the occultation of the 10.9 magnitude star TYC 2436-00120-1 by the asteroid 337 Devosa. The equipment consisted of a QHY174MGPS camera on a Celestron C8 w/Hyperstar v4, mounted on a ZWO AM5 harmonic mount in equatorial mode. I was not using a guide camera.

All devices were interconnected via a Pegasus Astro Pocket Power Box Advance to a HP I-5 laptop with 8 GB of RAM and an SSD hard drive. The computer is a former Win10 PC that I had installed the Win11 upgrade on a few months back. The active software included:

- SharpCap 4.1.12693.0
- ZWO AM5 ASCOM utility,
- Stellarium 25.2,
- Pocket Powerbox app, and the
- CelestronFocusUtility.

I prefer to set up my equipment about an hour before the event, but in this case I was awake so I went ahead and got everything in place and running about two hours before. I allowed the GPS to get a position and time lock and synchronized the PC clock. A recommendation had been made by another user of the QHY camera that I record the GPS log and watch for an almanac update from the satellites. This could take up to about 20 minutes, and results in the final clock synchronization with Universal Time. Until this happens the GPS time could be off by as much as 3 seconds. Which is significant when recording occultation timings.

While the GPS was getting the final time settings, I continued with the rest of my equipment setup. After the polar alignment was completed using SharpCap, I looked up the target star in Stellarium and had Stellarium move the mount to the target. Using tools in SharpCap, I plate solved and centered the target in the 1280 x 1024 ROI (region of interest) I had selected. Test exposures were acquired at various exposures and gain settings, resulting in a decision to go with 100 mSec exposures at 480 gain. I had also set

Occultation by 337 Devosa (cont.)

SharpCap to capture the GPS log file. Since this occultation was predicted to last 2.5 seconds, the 100 mSec exposure rate should result in approximately 25 data points during the event.

For about 40 minutes I was just letting everything run and waiting to start a SER movie capture of the occultation. At some point I noticed that Stellarium had become unresponsive, so I restarted it. Then, 5 minutes before the occultation, the computer crashed! **Panic Time!!** Allow the computer to reboot, and restart all software applications. I barely managed to get operational in time to start the data capture on the occultation. I actually started a few seconds later than planned, but I had allowed 45 secs each side of the occultation midpoint, so I had plenty of margin.

This was the first time I had turned on GPS data logging. Maybe just a coincidence, but it was also the first time my computer had ever totally crashed during a session. The GPS logging had been running from 07:55:59 UT until 09:45:13 UT, when the computer crashed. The log file was 15,684 KB.

This was my first recorded asteroid occultation that had bands of thin clouds moving across the target star. As a result, the first PyOTE analysis detected a much larger duration occultation than the prediction. This was due to light clouds dimming the image just before the actual occultation occurred. (See the image on the second page following.)

The Occult Watcher footer showing the locations on the asteroid's transverse cross section where the three declared stations were predicted to contact the asteroid's image.

Occultation by 337 Devosa (cont.)

An image of the region around the target star, plate solved and indicated by SharpCap.

Occultation by 337 Devosa (cont.)

The (initial, incorrect) PyOTE-generated data summary shown below indicated an occultation duration of 4.5 seconds, considerably greater than the prediction. Looking at the plot there are two plateaus of decreased magnitude detected. However, if one examines the comparison star data (the green dots), the comparison star magnitude also decreased during the first plateau, but was on the increase throughout the second magnitude drop.

Solution 'envelope' in the main plot drawn using 0.95 containment interval error bars

```
fit metrics for signal-Target
fit metrics === noiseSigmaDistance: 10.8
fit metrics === time error bar: +/- 0.0915 seconds
fit metrics === DNR: 4.63
fit metrics === B: 360424.15 A: 100235.75 sigmaB: 56144.30 sigmaA: 91243.96
fit metrics === magDrop report: percentDrop: 72.2 magDrop: 1.389 +/- 0.299 (0.95 ci)
fit metrics === D frame number: 600.5794
fit metrics === R frame number: 645.4253
fit metrics === duration: 4.5022 seconds
fit metrics === D time: [09:51:40.4598]
fit metrics === R time: [09:51:44.9620]
```

signal-Target is the target curve.

Occultation by 337 Devosa (cont.)

The following (corrected) image had a normalization factor applied to smooth the magnitude drops, using information from the comparison star spectrum (green dots). The initial plateau is completely eliminated, and now the data supports a 2.63 sec duration, much closer to the 2.5 sec duration predicted. This revised magnitude drop of about 2.7 is also consistent with expectations.

==== end Summary report for Excel file =====

Solution 'envelope' in the main plot drawn using 0.95 containment interval error bars

```
fit metrics for signal-Target
fit metrics === noiseSigmaDistance: 61.8
fit metrics === time error bar: +/- 0.0214 seconds
fit metrics === DNR: 8.28
fit metrics === B: 357749.29 A: 29710.97 sigmaB: 39638.13 sigmaA: 21428.36
fit metrics === magDrop report: percentDrop: 91.7 magDrop: 2.702 +/- 0.312 (0.95 ci)
fit metrics === D frame number: 619.1654
fit metrics === R frame number: 645.3278
fit metrics === duration: 2.6265 seconds
fit metrics === D time: [09:51:42.3257]
fit metrics === R time: [09:51:44.9522]
```

A Night in Cloudcroft

- Ted Barnes

The Southwest Desert is renowned among astronomers for having a remarkably clear and strikingly beautiful sky, provided that one chooses the proper location. Probably many of us have a fantasy of someday living under those skies, which may only be a Real Estate Agent away. For similar reasons late in Sep 2025 I found myself with my Mrs (Agatha) and adult daughter (Sietske) in Southern New Mexico, driving towards Alamogordo, where I had an appointment the next day to see a likely looking property near the famous little resort village of Cloudcroft. Of course one should not purchase a property without seeing it, and past experience suggests that one may not find the ideal site until several have been visited. But of course you need to start somewhere, so I had selected a pretty ranch house with 55 acres of surrounding desert as a first possibility from which to iterate. The distances were greater than I expected, so we didn't reach Alamogordo and its famous giant pistachio until about 7 pm, following which we turned Northeast and headed up New Mexico State Rd. 82 into the Sacramento Mountains. We checked in to our little room on Chipmunk Lane in Cloudcroft about 8 pm, and after Agatha transitioned into slumber around 8:30 pm,

Thu 25 Sep 2025

Sunset	6:56 pm
Civ dusk	7:21 pm
Ast dusk	8:18 pm
Moonrise	10:28 am
Moonset	8:48 pm

Moon illum. 13%

**Tzec Maun Observatory, nr. Cloudcroft.
No Moon during this event.**

2:24 pm. Heading South, warned of rattlesnakes.

3:34 pm. Well not exactly here.

A Night in Cloudcroft (cont.)

Sietske and I decided to go out and sample the local skies. In Cloudcroft itself there were high, bright white streetlights, and you could only see black sky without stars between them. We decided that a drive beyond the village limits was appropriate. After some confusion we chose New Mexico State Rd. 130, which continued South from Cloudcroft, and descended into a dark National Forest with a few open areas along the sides of the road. Not expecting anything especially notable, we drove for about 10 miles, and around 8:40 pm I stopped at a pulloff that seemed to be set low between two steep cliffs.

After I stopped the car Sietske climbed out of the passenger side, and I heard a soft exclamation. I climbed out the driver's side and looked up, left, right, and various directions. The sky was *intense*. Yes, I could see the Milky Way near Cassiopeia to my right, but that band of greyish light was *bright*, and one could easily see complicated structures and star clouds comprising the band. It was too much. I looked away and saw Boötes and Corona Borealis, the latter a garish circlet of glowing white, cream and reddish coals. Up again, and you saw more of the Milky Way. With silence, and maybe a hint of wind. And something else, something weird and unexpected.

It was very faint at first, and I thought I had imagined it, but when I listened very carefully, I could repeatedly hear a soft tinkle of music accompanying the stars. It seemed to drift in and out, a strange sci-fi kind of melody, with an even fainter, somewhat discordant background line. Was this really my imagination? Was someone in one of the sheds you could just make out in the darkness across the road, against the hillside, playing a little hint of music to celebrate the night sky? Might it even be another astronomer nearby with a little radio on for entertainment?

I asked Sietske if she had heard the faint music. Yes, she said, she heard it, but it wasn't music. What she heard was more of a faint, distant, screaming. And she was getting back in the car, now! I really didn't need to hear that, I was enjoying the stars so much, but the "music" continued, strange and discordant and perhaps disoriented. I decided that inside the car was the better place to be, so I climbed back in and we drove back towards Cloudcroft.

A Night in Cloudcroft (cont.)

Sietske said that was the most remarkable sky she had ever seen in her life, even as a hiker, with several years of experience with New Mexico. Perhaps because we were on a very dark road shielded by steep cliffs, and at an altitude of 8500 ft? She also said that she recognized the strange distant “music” that I had interpreted as other-worldly sci-fi / UFO type “Music from the Hearts of Space,” and she looked for an example of this faint cacophony on her cell phone. She had recognized it as the cry of a mountain lion. The locals know not to encounter mountain lions. I did manage to capture one cellphone image, to the Northwest, before getting back into the car. That image, enhanced, is at bottom left; some residual twilight is evident. Aldebaran is at image bottom left; image center is in Northern Boötes, at *ca.* RA 14.5h, Dec +50°N.

The next morning we met our Real Estate Agent in Alamogordo, and with her assistance we did visit the potential New Mexico observatory property. The house was very beautiful. There were complications, such as being 200 miles from Albuquerque, having “just” Bortle 3 skies (the same as the previous night), and most of the surrounding 55 acres being on various extreme slopes. The most important complication was that someone else had recently made an offer, so the property was likely no longer available. The following day we managed to visit White Sands and the Very Large Array near Socorro, and learned that “Pie Town,” West of the VLA, also had potential observatory properties available, *albeit* under **Bortle 1** skies. The search continues.

8:40 pm, 25 Sep 2025. 10 mi. S of Cloudcroft.

10:28 am, 26 Sep 2025. A potential observatory.

The Stargazey Events of Thu 02 Oct 2025

- Ted Barnes

Thu 02 Oct 2025

Sunset	7:20 pm
Civ dusk	7:45 pm
Ast dusk	8:45 pm
Moonrise	4:58 pm
Moonset*	3:26 am
	* 03 Oct

Moon illum. 74%

Waxing Gibbous Moon.

Bright Moon visible during this event.

Many things happened on this pleasant evening, so I will give a quick summary that will be somewhat unfair to all, especially since I don't recall exactly how the organization took place. In online discussions using WhatsApp I think Noah Frere had mentioned that he would be going to TAO early on this evening, as early as 5 pm, since he would be teaching a class of astronomy students and needed some time to prepare. Coincidentally some of us had noticed that there was an attractive possibility to observe an occultation that evening, involving the outer main belt asteroid 1298 Nocturna and an unusually bright star of g-magnitude 10.4 in the constellation Sagittarius. Of course this time of year observing anything in Sagittarius would be an early evening event, and the occultation would accordingly be an early one, at 8:33 pm. One would have to arrive and set up early, but this could mesh with Noah's plan to open TAO early, in the late afternoon. I expressed interest online, as did Rob Fowler and Art Allison. Don Spong also stated that he might arrive to take advantage of the opportunity for astrophotography. So, we had spontaneously organized an astronomy evening with at least five additional astronomers and Noah's group of students. *Alles gut!*

Don Spong setting up on the North pad while Noah's Roane State Astronomy class prepare a debate regarding the reality of the Apollo moon landings. 7:17 pm Eastern, 02 Oct 2025.

Stargazey Events of Thu 02 Oct 2025 (cont.)

Noah said that he would be using the Meade LX-200 with the students, so I brought along my Meade kit to help out. Since Rob was accordingly available to help me with capturing this early occultation, he rode with me for convenience, and planned to share a ride back relatively early. On arrival soon after 6 pm we began assembling my usual setup, and had everything ready to start realignment around 7:25 pm. (See image below.) A move requires a change of site location coordinates in CPWI, and usually a new alignment. In principle one can just load an old set of alignment stars and resync, but that shortcut is typically problematic. Turning CPWI and PHD2 on, I loaded an earlier TAO alignment set, and a slew to Kochab showed it nearly centered in the guide scope. I turned on SharpCap and centered Kochab and then Thuban, most promising, but I when tried a slew to nearby Alkaid it wasn't even in the guidescope's field. Also on the negative side, the laser was alternately weak or out, and SharpCap's plate solve tool failed to solve. About 8:00 pm Noah sent his rather large class over to our Northeast pad for a quick chat about our occultation plans. I handed out some hand-drawn occultation local field star charts I had prepared to Don and Noah, who had said they too might try to capture the occultation.

My occultation setup, largely complete, still lacking some cables and the monitor. Note my new safety device, a black net bag to capture the gps camera should its holding screws fail.

7:05 pm Eastern, 02 Oct 2025.

Stargazey Events of Thu 02 Oct 2025 (cont.)

Rob and I finished our discussion with the students around 8:11 pm, which left us with only about 20 minutes to align the telescope, find the target star, and prepare to capture the occultation. Well that was the problem of course, this was an EARLY event, and success would require that nothing go wrong. And here I was still muddling with finding Alkaid, far from Sagittarius. So I dropped that and tried a slew to Aldebaran, halfway to Sgr. It appeared in the guidescope! It was alas also in the one TAO tree, drat, and the OTA couldn't see it clearly. So I added it as best I could, and slewed to Sabik, η Oph. Nothing appeared. I kept trying to use SharpCap's plate solver tool, but it repeatedly failed to function. Rob told me I had about *five minutes* remaining until the 8:33 pm occultation. I tried a slew to Kaus Borealis, the lynchpin in the Sgr teapot, and a star appeared. No time to check anything. I added it to the alignment stars and did a final "Hail Mary" slew to the nominal coordinates of the target star, TYC 6859-00173-1, in NE Sgr. God knows where the OTA was actually pointing by then. Oh well, it's all good practice. The field didn't look much like my star chart, but this was the best I could do. Noah yelled from the glow dome that he would send his students over to watch the occultation, but I yelled back that we don't have it (the target star). Art volunteered to entertain the students. I set SharpCap to capture a 1000-exposure SER movie of 200ms frames at the maximum QHY174MGPS camera gain of 480, and at about 8:33:00 pm I began capturing frames. That was it. Nothing more I could do.

Art near the glow dome, capturing deep-sky images with his Seestar S50.

Stargazey Events of Thu 02 Oct 2025 (cont.)

Not long after the event, Don strolled by and told us he thought he had captured the occultation. He showed us some images on his tablet, with the star being “out” in at least two. I didn’t understand this since he said they were 200ms frames, but ok, if the star went out, he must have captured it! Good for him, but personally I was feeling demoralized. Things I was most unhappy about included 1) my green laser pointer, which kept going out whenever it was most needed, 2) SharpCap’s failure to plate solve, which I REALLY needed, 3) my inability to align this system at a remote location with CPWI and keep it aligned in future with the same stored set of alignment stars, 4) my PHD2 OTA guiding system, which really needs to be recalibrated, but according to the popup instructions that should only be done when the guidescope is pointed towards a suitable location in the sky, whatever that might be. This list could go on.

Anyway, after the event, with the time pressure off, I went back to adding more stars in Sgr to my set of alignment stars, repeatedly telling the system to slew to the known coordinates of the target star. Strangely, it kept going to almost the same location it had used before; I recognized that field by now. Might I have accidentally captured the event, despite the chaos of the last few minutes before the dreaded 8:33 pm?

When I compared the chart I drew from The Sky X (rotated by π) with an image I had captured of what might be the target star’s field, after some comparison I could see that the two fields really did coincide! (See next page.) Thus there was a good chance that the SER movie really did capture the occultation!

One of the puzzles that had thrown me in trying to identify the target star by comparing my chart (hand-drawn from The Sky X) to my camera images is evident on the next page. The Sky X shows a moderately bright star of magnitude 12.2, labelled GSC 6859:772, just below the target star. My captured image shows no such star. The Gaia database in Aladin v.12 shows a star at this location, Gaia EDR3 4078656701299780480, but it is much fainter, with a g-mag of only 15.4. Perhaps this is a long-term variable, or just a misidentified asteroid? In any case this apparent mistake in the chart (following page, top) is one reason I was unsure about whether we had actually found the correct target star, TYC 6859-00173-1.

Stargazey Events of Thu 02 Oct 2025 (cont.)

telescope image
08:41:10 pm Eastern, 2 Oct 2025
1x1sG480, 1920x1200 = ff, post proc.

Showing that the target star chart (top) and my telescope image (bottom) do coincide!

Stargazey Events of Thu 02 Oct 2025 (cont.)

Once it appeared likely that we really HAD captured the target star in our original SER movie of 8:33-35 pm, which had become evident about 10 pm, I felt brave enough to suggest to Rob that we actually watch the movie. Normally I prefer to take the images home and carefully identify each important field; jumping to the relevant SER movie file immediately at TAO seemed like tempting fate. However Rob was all for it, and since I had suggested it, we pretty much had no choice, if I was to avoid looking like a chicken. So, I loaded the 1000-exposure SER movie into the SER player and hit start. The first (gps-timed) exposure started at 08:33:01.315 pm Eastern, and the frames advanced in 200ms steps. The target star was surprisingly bright. When we reached about 08:33:36 pm THE STAR WENT OUT. It stayed out until about 08:33:39 pm. WE HAD CAPTURED THE OCCULTATION! I let out a number of undignified “yes!” noises, so much so that Art yelled over to ask if I was ok. Yes, Yes and Yes! We had captured the occultation by 1298 Nocturna after all!

At home on 3 Oct I used Pymovie and PyOTE to analyze the event in detail. With 1 σ error bars, the PyOTE square well fit has identified Disappearance and Reappearance times (Eastern) of D = 08:33:36.484(8) pm and R = 08:33:39.063(8) pm, giving a duration of 2.58(1) secs. These observations are consistent with predictions, but have much smaller errors, of about a hundredth of a second. The fit cites a magnitude drop of 5.2 \pm 0.7, also consistent with expectations. A plot of my fitted occultation data is shown below.

Here the upper (purple) points are from a comparison star, the middle (dark blue) points that show the occultation are from the target star, and the pale blue points at bottom are from an empty “no star” aperture of the same size, as an indication of the background count level.

What is especially interesting is that Richard Piety also captured this event at his home observatory RPO in Powell, which is a considerable distance from TAO. This will allow some interesting future comparisons.

Stargazey Events of Thu 02 Oct 2025 (cont.)

The basic information extracted in a simple occultation are the target star's disappearance time D, reappearance time R, and the duration of the event, which is the difference R-D. In Richard's case the values determined by pymovie and pyote at 1σ significance are as follows:

$$D = \text{UT } 00:33:39.3537(39)$$

$$R = \text{UT } 00:33:42.0200(39)$$

$$\text{Dur} = R - D = 2.6663(54) \text{ secs.}$$

In comparison at TAO I had

$$D = \text{UT } 00:33:36.4835(85)$$

$$R = \text{UT } 00:33:39.0633(85)$$

$$\text{Dur} = R - D = 2.5798(121) \text{ secs.}$$

The difference in durations,

$$\Delta\text{Dur} = 0.087(13) \text{ secs}$$

is statistically significant, and is an observation that the shadow of the asteroid, and hence the duration of the occultation, is longer near the shadow midline. TAO was 8.5 km from the centerline, whereas Richard's RPO was 6.1 km from the centerline. Given an estimated diameter of 40 km, and a predicted max dur of 2.5 secs, if we assume a circular shadow, the duration at RPO should be longer than the duration at TAO by 0.12 secs, comparable to what was observed. This is a first step towards measuring an asteroid's profile. Similarly, the disappearance at RPO was predicted to be about 3 secs later than at TAO, and the actual difference was $\Delta D = 2.87(9)$ secs. From the known shadow velocity we can infer that Richard's site RPO is roughly 43 km from TAO. An actual comparison of these distances will be followed up in the next issue.

Public Stargaze of 04 Oct 2025

- Ted Barnes

Although the weather predictions suggested that the skies for this Sat night would not be the best, and Sun might be somewhat better, David decided to proceed as usual, and urged the usual astronomy types to arrive by 8:00 pm. I actually arrived somewhat earlier, about 7:30 pm, without equipment (I was still recovering from the 02 Oct occultation), but with Meade box in tow to help with visitors. Initially I only encountered Rob, but soon David appeared, as did Noah's student Paige and friend Aaron. Art and Don also appeared, with Janet Spong, as did Bob Edwards and Robert Corliss, so we had an ample supply of astronomers as well as interesting characters. Gradually the number of visitors increased, until we had something like

Sat 04 Oct 2025

Sunset	7:18 pm
Civ dusk	7:44 pm
Ast dusk	8:43 pm
Moonrise	5:58 pm
Moonset*	5:46 am
	* 05 Oct

Moon illum. 91%

Waxing Gibbous Moon.
Nearly Full Moon during this event.

The view to the West, 7:47 pm Eastern, 02 Oct 2025.

Public Stargaze of 04 Oct 2025 (cont.)

ten. It's always interesting hearing their stories regarding TAO; our three front row visitors were from Rockwood, and knew that the observatory was here, but had never visited. They hoped to see the Andromeda galaxy through a large telescope.

As usual we provided a quick set of astronomy lectures for our visitors. David gave his TAO overview talk, I told them about asteroid occultations and showed them results from just two nights before, and Don gave an extensive astrophotography talk covering our solar system, stars, star clusters and nebulae within our galaxy, and finally, images of external galaxies. This was in essence a quick tour of the universe.

After the presentations we noted that the sky had improved beyond expectations, as is often the case, so we accompanied the visitors outside, to discuss astronomy and view what was on offer at the Meade.

Don Spong explaining his remarkable images. 9:09 pm Eastern, 04 Oct 2025.

Public Stargaze of 04 Oct 2025 (cont.)

Since the Moon was very bright, Rob first showed lunar views to our visitors; since it was not quite full, there were enjoyable views of craters and mountains. Reminder: add a moon filter to the Meade kit. Subsequently he showed Saturn to our visitors; it continues to present a lovely disk with a short dash through it.

Above: Some of our astronomers and guests discussing the sky and related issues near the large dome. The Moon was so bright that even identifying the Great Square of Pegasus was a challenge. Fun events included viewing the Moon and Saturn through the Meade, and identifying Capella and the Pleiades near the Eastern horizon. 10:01 pm Eastern, 04 Oct 2025.

Public Stargaze of 04 Oct 2025 (cont.)

For some time after our visitors departed, Rob and Ted experimented with using the HC to launch various slews on the Meade-LX200. The results were not especially consistent. It was clear that the Home position was something like 5 degrees to the left of Polaris; Rob left the system in Hibernate, directed towards Polaris, but this probably needs a platform adjustment; another evening of Meade alignment improvement exercises is appropriate. Methods that worked for resetting the Home position on the Meade previously were recorded in loving detail by moi in a series of “Work on the Meade” articles in the Trapezium in late 2024. In the Dec 2024 issue I provided a detailed discussion of information that is (and is not) available in the GGE online manual, see especially pp.33-36 in that issue. The alignment of the mount platform in Alt and Azi is discussed there, and is straightforward, although one part is a “workaround.” A small Allan key set is needed, including 3/16” and 7/32” keys. Enjoy!

The glowdome and associated discussion groups, 10:01-pm Eastern, 04 Oct 2025. Visible at upper left is bright Fomalhaut, and at middle left, surprisingly, γ Gruis. At upper right, receding into the trees, is part of the Sagittarius teapot. At middle right just above the treeline is α Sgr. The eagle-eyed may even find the very obscure La Caille creation Microscopium.

The evening Sky Map for October 2025 from skymaps.com.

The Evening Sky Map

FREE* EACH MONTH FOR YOU TO EXPLORE, LEARN & ENJOY THE NIGHT SKY

NORTHERN HEMISPHERE OCTOBER 2025

Sky Calendar - October 2025

Follow us on Bluesky
skymaps.com/bsky/

- 2 Dwarf planet 1 Ceres at opposition at 4h UT. Mag. 7.6.
 - 4 International Observe the Moon Night
Join the global celebration at moon.nasa.gov/observe
 - 6 Moon near Saturn at 1h UT (evening sky). Mag. 0.7.
 - 7 Full Moon at 3:48 UT.
 - 8 Comet C/2025 K1 (ATLAS) at perihelion. Mag. 9.4 (est.)
 - 8 Moon at perigee (closest to Earth) at 12:50 UT (distance 359,819km; angular size 33.2").
 - 10 Moon near the Pleiades at 6h UT (morning sky).
 - 13 Last Quarter Moon at 18:13 UT.
 - 14 Moon near Jupiter at 1h UT (morning sky). Mag. -2.2.
 - 16 Moon near Regulus at 19h UT (morning sky).
 - 19 Moon near Venus at 19h UT (19° from Sun, morning sky). Mag. -3.9.
 - 19 Mercury 2.0° SSW of Mars at 21h UT (22° from Sun, evening sky). Mags. -0.2 and 1.5.
 - 20 Comet C/2025 R2 (SWAN) makes its closest approach to Earth (0.26 AU). Mag. 7.1 (est.)
 - 21 Comet C/2025 A6 (Lemmon) makes its closest approach to Earth (0.60 AU). Mag. 3.2 (est.)
 - 21 Orionid meteor shower peaks. Arises from the debris field of Comet Halley. Active from October 2 to November 7. Produces very fast (67 km/sec), generally faint meteors (10-20 per hour). Radiant located near Orion's club asterism.
 - 25 New Moon at 12:25 UT. Start of lunation 1272.
 - 23 Moon, Mercury and Mars within 4.3° circle at 11h UT (22° from Sun, evening sky). Mags. -0.2 and 1.5.
 - 24 Moon at apogee (farthest from Earth) at 0h UT (distance 406,444km; angular size 29.4").
 - 25 Moon near Antares at 2h UT (evening sky).
 - 29 First Quarter Moon at 16:21 UT.
 - 29 Interstellar Comet 3I/ATLAS at perihelion. Mag. 11.7 (est.)
 - 29 Mercury at easternmost elongation at 22h UT (evening sky). Mag. -0.1.
- More sky events and links at <http://Skymaps.com/skycalendar/>
All times in Universal Time (UT). (USA Eastern Daylight Time = UT - 4 hours.)

SKY MAP SHOWS HOW THE NIGHT SKY LOOKS
EARLY OCT 8 PM
LATE OCT 7 PM
(Add 1 Hour For Daylight Saving)
 SKY MAP DRAWN FOR A LATITUDE OF 40° NORTH AND IS SUITABLE FOR LATITUDES UP TO 15° NORTH OR SOUTH OF THIS

- Symbols**
- Galaxy ☾
 - Double Star ●●
 - Variable Star ●
 - Diffuse Nebula □
 - Planetary Nebula ◇
 - Open Star Cluster ○
 - Globular Star Cluster ⊙

Star Magnitudes -1 ● 0 ● 1 ● 2 ● 3 ● 4

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Note: a nice interactive sky chart from Sky and Telescope may be found at the link <https://skyandtelescope.org/interactive-sky-chart/>

The evening Sky Map for October 2025 from skymaps.com.

About the Celestial Objects

Listed on this page are several of the brighter, more interesting celestial objects visible in the evening sky this month (refer to the monthly sky map). The objects are grouped into three categories. Those that can be easily seen with the naked eye (that is, without optical aid), those easily seen with binoculars, and those requiring a telescope to be appreciated. **Note, all of the objects (except single stars) will appear more impressive when viewed through a telescope or very large binoculars.** They are grouped in this way to highlight objects that can be seen using the optical equipment that may be available to the star gazer.

Tips for Observing the Night Sky

When observing the night sky, and in particular deep-sky objects such as star clusters, nebulae, and galaxies, it's always best to observe from a dark location. Avoid direct light from street lights and other sources. If possible observe from a dark location away from the light pollution that surrounds many of today's large cities.

You will see more stars after your eyes adapt to the darkness—usually about 10 to 20 minutes after you go outside. Also, if you need to use a torch to view the sky map, cover the light bulb with red cellophane. This will preserve your dark vision.

Finally, even though the Moon is one of the most stunning objects to view through a telescope, its light is so bright that it brightens the sky and makes many of the fainter objects very difficult to see. So try to observe the evening sky on moonless nights around either New Moon or Last Quarter.

Astronomical Glossary

Conjunction – An alignment of two celestial bodies such that they present the least angular separation as viewed from Earth.

Constellation – A defined area of the sky containing a star pattern.

Diffuse Nebula – A cloud of gas illuminated by nearby stars.

Double Star – Two stars that appear close to each other in the sky; either linked by gravity so that they orbit each other (binary star) or lying at different distances from Earth (optical double). Apparent separation of stars is given in seconds of arc (").

Ecliptic – The path of the Sun's center on the celestial sphere as seen from Earth.

Elongation – The angular separation of two celestial bodies. For Mercury and Venus the greatest elongation occurs when they are at their most angular distance from the Sun as viewed from Earth.

Galaxy – A mass of up to several billion stars held together by gravity.

Globular Star Cluster – A ball-shaped group of several thousand old stars.

Light Year (ly) – The distance a beam of light travels at 300,000 km/sec in one year.

Magnitude – The brightness of a celestial object as it appears in the sky.

Open Star Cluster – A group of tens or hundreds of relatively young stars.

Opposition – When a celestial body is opposite the Sun in the sky.

Planetary Nebula – The remnants of a shell of gas blown off by a star.

Universal Time (UT) – A time system used by astronomers. Also known as Greenwich Mean Time. USA Eastern Standard Time (for example, New York) is 5 hours behind UT.

Variable Star – A star that changes brightness over a period of time.

NORTHERN HEMISPHERE
OCTOBER 2025

CELESTIAL OBJECTS
Skymaps.com

Easily Seen with the Naked Eye

Altair	Aql	• Brightest star in Aquila. Name means "the flying eagle". Dist-16.7 ly.
Capella	Aur	• The 6th brightest star. Appears yellowish in color. Spectroscopic binary. Dist-42 ly.
Arcturus	Boo	• Orange, giant K star. Name means "bear watcher". Dist-36.7 ly.
δ Cephei	Cep	• Cepheid prototype. Mag varies between 3.5 & 4.4 over 5.366 days. Mag 6 companion.
Deneb	Cyg	• Brightest star in Cygnus. One of the greatest known supergiants. Dist-1,400±200 ly.
α Herculis	Her	• Semi-regular variable. Magnitude varies between 3.1 & 3.9 over 90 days. Mag 5.4 companion.
Vega	Lyr	• The 5th brightest star in the sky. A blue-white star. Dist-25.0 ly.
Algol	Per	• Famous eclipsing binary star. Magnitude varies between 2.1 & 3.4 over 2.867 days.
Fomalhaut	PSa	• Brightest star in Piscis Austrinus. In Arabic the "fish's mouth". Dist-25 ly.
Pleiades	Tau	• The Seven Sisters. Spectacular cluster. Many more stars visible in binoculars. Dist-380 ly.
Polaris	UMi	• The North Pole Star. A telescope reveals an unrelated mag 8 companion star. Dist-433 ly.

Easily Seen with Binoculars

M31	And	• The Andromeda Galaxy. Most distant object visible to naked eye. Dist-2.93 million ly.
M2	Aqr	• Resembles a fuzzy star in binoculars.
η Aquilae	Aql	• Bright Cepheid variable. Mag varies between 3.6 & 4.5 over 7.166 days. Dist-1,200 ly.
μ Cephei	Cep	• Herschel's Garnet Star. One of the reddest stars. Mag 3.4 to 5.1 over 730 days.
γ Cygni	Cyg	• Long period pulsating red giant. Magnitude varies between 3.3 & 14.2 over 407 days.
M39	Cyg	• May be visible to the naked eye under good conditions. Dist-900 ly.
ν Draconis	Dra	• Wide pair of white stars. One of the finest binocular pairs in the sky. Dist-100 ly.
M13	Her	• Best globular in northern skies. Discovered by Halley in 1714. Dist-23,000 ly.
M92	Her	• Fainter and smaller than M13. Use a telescope to resolve its stars.
ε Lyrae	Lyr	• Famous Double Double. Binoculars show a double star. High power reveals each a double.
R Lyrae	Lyr	• Semi-regular variable. Magnitude varies between 3.9 & 5.0 over 46.0 days.
M12	Oph	• Close to the brighter M10. Dist-18,000 ly.
M10	Oph	• 3 degrees from the fainter M12. Both may be glimpsed in binoculars. Dist-14,000 ly.
IC 4665	Oph	• Large, scattered open cluster. Visible with binoculars.
6633	Oph	• Scattered open cluster. Visible with binoculars.
M15	Peg	• Only globular known to contain a planetary nebula (Mag 14, d=1"). Dist-30,000 ly.
Double Cluster	Per	• Double Cluster in Perseus. NGC 869 & 884. Excellent in binoculars. Dist-7,300 ly.
M8	Sgr	• Lagoon Nebula. Bright nebula bisected by a dark lane. Dist-5,200 ly.
M25	Sgr	• Bright cluster located about 6 deg N of "teapot's" lid. Dist-1,900 ly.
M22	Sgr	• A spectacular globular star cluster. Telescope will show stars. Dist-10,000 ly.
Mizar & Alcor	UMa	• Good eyesight or binoculars reveals 2 stars. Not a binary. Mizar has a mag 4 companion.
Cr 399	Vul	• Coathanger asterism or "Brooch's Cluster". Not a true star cluster. Dist-218 to 1,140 ly.

Telescopic Objects

γ Andromedae	And	• Attractive double star. Bright orange star with mag 5 blue companion. Sep-9.8".
7009	Aqr	• Saturn Nebula. Requires 8-inch telescope to see Saturn-like appendages.
7293	Aqr	• Helix Nebula. Spans nearly 1/4 deg. Requires dark sky. Dist-300 ly.
γ Arietis	Ari	• Impressive looking double blue-white star. Visible in a small telescope. Sep-7.8".
M51	CvN	• Whirlpool Galaxy. First recognised to have spiral structure. Dist-25 million ly.
η Cassiopeiae	Cas	• Yellow star mag 3.4 & orange star mag 7.5. Dist-19 ly. Orbit-480 years. Sep-12".
Albireo	Cyg	• Beautiful double star. Contrasting colours of orange and blue-green. Sep-34.4".
61 Cygni	Cyg	• Attractive double star. Mags 5.2 & 6.1 orange dwarfs. Dist-11.4 ly. Sep-28.4".
γ Delphini	Del	• Appear yellow & white. Mags 4.3 & 5.2. Dist-100 ly. Struve 2725 double in same field.
β Lyrae	Lyr	• Eclipsing binary. Mag varies between 3.3 & 4.3 over 12.940 days. Fainter mag 7.2 blue star.
M57	Lyr	• Ring Nebula. Magnificent object. Smoke-ring shape. Dist-4,100 ly.
M23	Sgr	• Elongated star cluster. Telescope required to show stars. Dist-2,100 ly.
M20	Sgr	• Trifid Nebula. A telescope shows 3 dust lanes trisecting nebula. Dist-5,200 ly.
M21	Sgr	• A fine and impressive cluster. Dist-4,200 ly.
M17	Sgr	• Omega Nebula. Contains the star cluster NGC 6618. Dist-4,900 ly.
M11	Sct	• Wild Duck Cluster. Resembles a globular through binoculars. V-shaped. Dist-5,600 ly.
M16	Ser	• Eagle Nebula. Requires a telescope of large aperture. Dist-8,150 ly.
M33	Tri	• Fine face-on spiral galaxy. Requires a large aperture telescope. Dist-2.3 million ly.
M81	UMa	• Beautiful spiral galaxy visible with binoculars. Easy to see in a telescope.
M27	Vul	• Dumbbell Nebula. Large, twin-lobed shape. Most spectacular planetary. Dist-975 ly.

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Note: a nice interactive sky chart from Sky and Telescope may be found at the link <https://skyandtelescope.org/interactive-sky-chart/>

Astrophotography

Titan and shadow transiting Saturn

- John Cliff

Despite questionable weather predictions, Noah Frere and John Cliff decided to set up for planetary imaging of Titan's eclipse of Saturn at John's home on September 19, as it was the last chance to catch such an alignment until the year 2040. The pair were rewarded for their persistence as the clouds started to clear at around 02:45 on the 20th. Despite marginal transparency, Cliff was able to capture the last part of the eclipse using the technique of lucky imaging. Out of about 15,000 25ms frames acquired for each broadband filter (red, green, and blue), the best 15% were chosen, stacked, derotated, and sharpened using freely available software. Titan is visible below and left of its shadow on Saturn's outermost cloud bands in the processed image. The technique of lucky imaging for planetary and lunar astrophotography will be covered in a future ORION seminar.

Veil Nebulae

- Don Spong

This month I've worked on imaging the Veil Nebulae in the constellation Cygnus. Cygnus is in a good position directly overhead from August through early October. I had imaged these nebulas earlier, but wanted to revisit them with my new camera. The following two images are parts of a larger loop structure in Cygnus and ideally, if time were available, it would be nice to assemble mosaics that would put all of these parts into one integrated image. However, I haven't had time to do that.

These nebulae were created by the explosion of a star about 20 times more massive than our sun, 10,000 to 20,000 years ago. The image below is the Western Veil Nebula, and the following is the Eastern Veil Nebula. These were taken on September 20 and 29 using my Celestron Edge HD, ZWO AM5 mount, Hyperstar attachment, ZWO 2600 MCPPro camera, Williams Optics guide scope, ZWO 220MM guide camera, Antlia triband filter, all controlled by my ZWO ASI AIR. Around sixty 60-second images were stacked to form these images.

The Western Veil Nebula

Veil Nebulae (cont.)

The Eastern Veil Nebula

Appendices

Astronomy

- tb

Some numbers are quoted to several-digit accuracy where appropriate.
Exact numerical relationships are indicated as such.

1 ly = 1 ly (Julian) = *exactly* 9 460 730 472 580. 8 km = 63 241. 077 084 ... AU
c = speed of light = *exactly* 299 792 458 m/s = *exactly* ☺ 1 ly/yr.
1 AU = *exactly* 149 597 870. 7 km
1 parsec (pc) = 3. 261 598 ... light years (ly)
1 yr (Julian) = *exactly* 365.25 d = *exactly* 31 557 600 s
1 d = *exactly* 86 400 s

distance to α Cen A = 1.346(2) pc = 4.390(8) ly
distance to the center of the galaxy ~ 8 kpc ~ 25 kly (considerable uncertainty)

1 nm = 1 nanometer = 10^{-9} m *exactly*
 H_{α} wavelength = 656.2 nm

+ 0.5 change in magnitude	= <i>exactly</i> $10^{1/5}$ x fainter =	1. 584 893 ... x fainter
+ 1 change in magnitude	= <i>exactly</i> $10^{2/5}$ x fainter =	2. 511 886 ... x fainter
+ 2 change in magnitude	= <i>exactly</i> $10^{4/5}$ x fainter =	6. 309 ... x fainter
+ 2.5 change in mag	= <i>exactly</i> 10^1 x fainter =	10 x fainter
+ 3 change in mag	= <i>exactly</i> $10^{6/5}$ x fainter =	15. 848 ... x fainter
+ 4 change in mag	= <i>exactly</i> $10^{8/5}$ x fainter =	39. 810 ... x fainter
+ 5 change in mag	= <i>exactly</i> 10^2 x fainter =	100 x fainter
+ 6 change in mag	= <i>exactly</i> $10^{12/5}$ x fainter =	251. 188 ... x fainter
+ 7.5 change in mag	= <i>exactly</i> 10^3 x fainter =	1000 x fainter
+ 8 change in mag	= <i>exactly</i> $10^{16/5}$ x fainter =	1584. 893 ... x fainter
+ 10 change in mag	= <i>exactly</i> 10^4 x fainter =	10 000 x fainter
+ 20 change in mag	= <i>exactly</i> 10^8 x fainter =	100 000 000 x fainter

Brightness is proportional to $1 / \text{distance}^2$

10 x more distant = *exactly* 10^2 x fainter = + 5 change in magnitude
 10^2 x more distant = *exactly* 10^4 x fainter = + 10 change in mag
 10^3 x more distant = *exactly* 10^6 x fainter = + 15 change in mag

Absolute magnitude M_{abs} is the brightness as seen from a distance of 10 pc.
 M_{abs} (our sun) = 4.83

17th mag is about 1 optical photon / $\text{cm}^2 \text{ s}$ (Barnes's rule ☺).

Astronomy (cont.)

Some numbers are quoted to several-digit accuracy where appropriate.
Exact numerical relationships are indicated as such.

R.A. = RA = Right Ascension = the angle ϕ around the celestial polar axis, usually quoted in hours, minutes, and seconds (*h m s*); analogous to longitude.

Dec = Declination = the angle θ above the celestial equator, usually quoted in degrees, minutes, and seconds ($^{\circ} \ ' \ ''$); analogous to latitude.

The RA (ϕ) and Dec (θ) angles, together with a reference epoch such as J2000.0, specify an object's direction in the sky.

A unit length vector ("unit vector") η pointing towards an object in the sky ("on the celestial sphere") in terms of RA (ϕ) and Dec (θ) angles is given by

$$\eta = \cos(\theta) \cos(\phi) \mathbf{x} + \cos(\theta) \sin(\phi) \mathbf{y} + \sin(\theta) \mathbf{z} = C (c \mathbf{x} + s \mathbf{y}) + S \mathbf{z}$$

The arc angle Θ_{12} between any two directions in the sky η_1 and η_2 (or any two stars) using the dot product formula and some obvious abbreviations, satisfies

$$\cos(\Theta_{12}) = \sin(\theta_1)\sin(\theta_2) + \cos(\theta_1)\cos(\theta_2)\cos(\phi_1-\phi_2) = S_1S_2 + C_1C_2c_{1-2}$$

$$1 \text{ degree} = \pi/180 \text{ radians} = 1.745 \cdot 10^{-2} \text{ radians}$$

$$1 \text{ arcmin} = \pi/10800 \text{ radians} = 2.909 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ radians}$$

$$1 \text{ arcsec} = 1 \text{ asec} = \pi/648000 \text{ radians} = 4.848 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ radians}$$

$$1 \text{ mas} = 10^{-3} \text{ asec} = 4.848 \cdot 10^{-9} \text{ radians}$$

$$1 \text{ asec @ 1 km} = 4.848 \text{ mm}$$

$$1 \text{ asec @ 1 AU} = 725.3 \text{ km}$$

$$1 \text{ asec @ 1 pc} = 1.0000 \text{ AU}$$

$$1 \text{ mas @ 1 kpc} = 1.0000 \text{ AU}$$

$$\text{Image scale [asec/px]} = 206.3 * \text{pixel size}[\mu\text{m}] / \text{focal length [mm]}$$

JD = Julian Date (Astronomer's calendar) = a simple count of days starting at noon UT on Monday 1 Jan 4713 BC. That date and time was the start of Julian Day 0. The current JD can be inferred from the value on the cover of the Trapezium.

The 80 Brightest Stars

The 80 brightest stars (c/o Wikipedia), and their distances from Earth in light years, with errors (from Gaia data, or Simbad if needed as an alternative).

1	Sirius	8.709	0.0054	41	Menkalinan	81.1	0.46
2	Canopus	309.	16.	42	Atria	390.6	7.0
3	alpha Centauri A	4.395	0.0083	43	Alhena	109.3	8.2
4	Arcturus	36.72	0.22	44	Peacock	178.8	5.1
5	Vega	25.04	0.069	45	Alsephina	80.6	0.78
6	Capella	42.81	0.26	46	Mirzam	492.7	16.4
7	Rigel	863.	78.	47	Polaris	432.6	6.3
8	Procyon	11.46	0.051	48	Alphard	180.3	1.8
9	Archenar	139.4	3.4	49	Hamal	65.8	0.33
10	Betelgeuse	498.	63.	50	Diphda	96.3	0.46
11	beta Centauri	392.	24.	51	Mizar	81.1	0.93
12	Altair	16.73	0.049	52	Nunki	227.8	4.6
13	alpha Crucis	322.	16.	53	Menkent	58.8	0.21
14	Aldebaran	66.64	1.05	54	Alpheratz	97.0	1.01
15	Antares	554.	94.	55	Mirach	197.4	6.7
16	Spica	250.	13.	56	Rasalhague	48.6	0.77
17	Pollux	33.78	0.09	57	Algieba	130.1	2.7
18	Fomalhaut	25.13	0.09	58	Kochab	130.9	0.63
19	Deneb	1410	200	59	Saiph	974.	37.
20	Mimosa	279.	23.	60	Denebola	35.9	0.21
21	Regulus	79.30	0.67	61	Algol	89.9	3.47
22	Adhara	405.	7.0	62	Tiaki	177.0	4.0
23	Castor	50.68	0.032	63	Muhlifain	130.2	1.5
24	Shaula	571.2	7.5	64	Aspidiske	765.6	18.0
25	Gacrux	88.56	0.43	65	Suhail	544.5	10.0
26	Bellatrix	252.4	10.2	66	Alphecca	77.2	1.79
27	Elnath	133.9	1.9	67	Mintaka	692.5	85.
28	Miaplacidus	113.2	0.43	68	Sadr	1830	270
29	Alnilam	1980	540	69	Eltanin	154.3	0.7
30	Regor	1120	110	70	Schedar	231.5	8.2
31	Alnair	101.0	0.66	71	Naos	1080	40
32	Alnitak	736.	106.	72	Almach	393.0	49.
33	Alioth	82.55	0.42	73	Caph	54.7	0.35
34	Dubhe	122.9	2.2	74	Izar	235.9	8.4
35	Mirfak	506.	13.	75	alpha Lupi	464.6	11.
36	Wezen	1610	300	76	epsilon Centauri	427.5	27.
37	Sargas	300.	41.	77	Dschubba	491.2	66.
38	Kaus Australis	143.3	1.5	78	Larawag	63.7	0.27
39	Avior	605.	47.	79	eta Centauri	305.7	6.0
40	Alkaid	103.9	0.79	80	Merak	84.5	2.5

Notable Star-Pair Angles

Notable star pairs (from the set of the 80 brightest stars listed above) that are close to a multiple of 5° separation. The angles are in degrees.

		Θ	$\Delta\theta$	defect (%)
Schedar	Caph	5	-0.085	1.7
Betelgeuse	Alnitak	10	0.017	0.17
Capella	Castor	30	-0.023	0.077
Procyon	Mirzam	30	-0.094	0.31
Elnath	Alnilam	30	-0.096	0.32
Alpheratz	Caph	30	0.060	0.20
Aldebaran	Pollux	45	0.013	0.029
Betelgeuse	Algol	50	-0.033	0.066
Alnitak	Naos	50	-0.049	0.098
Pollux	Alioth	60	0.065	0.11
Gacrux	Alphard	60	-0.001	0.002
Regulus	Bellatrix	70	-0.030	0.043
Sirius	Mirfak	80	-0.094	0.12
alpha_Centauri	Regulus	90	0.057	0.063
Vega	Denebola	90	-0.065	0.072
Fomalhaut	Caph	90	0.006	0.007
Deneb	Alnilam	120	0.059	0.049
Menkent	Mintaka	120	0.000	0.000
Sirius	Alphecca	135	-0.089	0.066
Aldebaran	Antares	170	-0.021	0.012

Exeunt

What the British had to say about their geography during the Dark Ages:

The Land of Britain

The island of Britain lies virtually at the end of the world, towards the west and north-west. Poised in the divine scales that (we are told) weigh the whole Earth, it stretches from the south-west towards the northern pole. It has a length of eight hundred miles, a width of two hundred: leaving out of account the various large headlands that jut out between the curving ocean bays. It is fortified on all sides by a vast and more or less uncrossable ring of sea, apart from the straits on the south where one can cross to Belgic Gaul; but it has the benefit of estuaries of a number of streams, and especially two splendid rivers, the Thames and the Severn, arms of the sea along which luxuries from overseas used to be brought by ship. It is ornamented with twenty-eight cities and a number of castles, and well equipped with fortifications - walls, castellated towers, gates and houses, whose sturdily built roofs reared menacingly skyward. Like a chosen bride arrayed in a variety of jewellery, the island is decorated with wide plains and agreeably set hills, excellent for vigorous agriculture, and mountains especially suited to varying the pasture for animals. Flowers of varying hues underfoot make them a delightful picture. To water it, the island has clear fountains, whose constant flow drives before it pebbles white as snow, and brilliant rivers that glide with gentle murmur, guaranteeing sweet sleep for those who lie on their banks, and lakes flowing over with a cold rush of living water.

Gildas, "De Excidio Britonum"
ca. 540 A.D.

ORION and TAO (and Obed) General Information (links)

May be found at the following URLs:

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Tamke-Allan_Observatory

<http://www.orioninc.org/>

<https://orionastronomy.wordpress.com>

<https://www.facebook.com/ORIONAstronomyTN/>

<https://www.facebook.com/groups/454645124557215>

<https://www.facebook.com/pages/Tamke-Allan%20Observatory/120477734665841>

<https://www.roanestate.edu/?349-Tamke-Allan-Observatory>

<https://www.roanestate.edu/pages/obs/index.htm>

<https://twitter.com/TAOremote>

ORIONastronomy@groups.io

Where is TAO? (Bortle 4)

334 Caney Creek Rd, Rockwood, TN 37854

Gdome = N 35° 49' 56.6", W 84° 37' 03.8"; Alt. 322 m

NE Pad = N 35° 49' 57.4", W 84° 37' 03.1"; Alt. 322 m

Where is Obed? (Bortle 4)

Lilly Bluff Overlook

N 36° 06' 09", W 84° 43' 17"; Alt. 402 m

Nemo Bridge (on the bridge, E bank of Emory River)

N 36° 04' 07", W 84° 39' 43"; Alt. 268 m

Trapezium back issues online, at CERN's zenodo database:

A full CERN zenodo doi url is for example <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8219253>;
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Vol. 49, Issue 4; Fri 15 Apr 2023:	zenodo.org/records/8219253
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Vol. 50, Issue 09, Fri 13 Sep 2024:	13742825
Vol. 50, Issue 10, Fri 11 Oct 2024:	13921735
Vol. 50, Issue 11, Fri 15 Nov 2024:	14171218
Vol. 50, Issue 12, Fri 13 Dec 2024:	14394899
Vol. 51, Issue 01, Fri 10 Jan 2025:	14630165
Vol. 51, Issue 02, Fri 14 Feb 2025:	14873015
Vol. 51, Issue 03, Fri 14 Mar 2025:	15015954
Vol. 51, Issue 04, Fri 11 Apr 2025:	15200349
Vol. 51, Issue 05, Fri 16 May 2025:	15443035
Vol. 51, Issue 06, Fri 13 Jun 2025:	15660329
Vol. 51, Issue 07, Fri 11 Jul 2025:	15865574

Trapezium back issues online, at CERN's zenodo database:

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Vol. 51, Issue 8; Fri 15 Aug 2025: zenodo.org/records/16884202

Vol. 51, Issue 9; Fri 12 Sep 2025: [17108361](https://zenodo.org/records/17108361)

Vol. 51, Issue 10; Fri 10 Oct 2025: [17316280](https://zenodo.org/records/17316280)

A generic link that lists Trapezium pdf issues (and other ORION documents) starting with the most recent, which does not require a specific zenodo document number, follows:

<https://zenodo.org/communities/rigel/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest>

Fin du journal

Frannie the Astrocat at home, 1 Aug 2025.

Full of energy and enthusiasm for the next issue!